

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: COMPAORE****FIRST NAME: RODRIGUE W.****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student did use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 17%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11 Enterprise

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What should you include in the conclusion of an academic essay?
 - The conclusion should summarize the answer to the question, recapitulate the main points, and have a closing statement without introducing new information.¹**
 - The conclusion should present further arguments to support the thesis.
 - The conclusion should repeat the introduction without summarizing the key points.
 - The conclusion should end with a quotation or an open-ended question without concluding.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 11.

2. After the literature search, what is the next step before writing the academic essay?
- Detailed introduction.
 - Summarize the documents found.
 - Organize your ideas by drafting a detailed plan according to the points you intend to address.²**
 - Make new notes on the papers.
3. What are the key steps in documentary research?
- The critical steps of documentary research are collecting, analyzing, synthesizing, and writing.
 - The critical steps of documentary research are planning, collecting, evaluating, and citing sources.³**
 - The key steps of documentary research include source identification, note-taking, critical analysis, and report writing.
 - The key steps in documentary research are defining the subject, finding sources, assessing relevance, and synthesizing information.
4. How can you effectively integrate quotes and paraphrases into your writing while avoiding plagiarism?
- It is not necessary to provide citations for paraphrased information.

² Ibid., 9.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 536.

- Employ quotation marks for direct quotes and paraphrases to indicate the source.
 - Change the wording of a quote slightly and omit the citation to avoid plagiarism.
 - Always provide proper citations for both direct quotes and paraphrases to give credit to the source.⁴**
5. When you use both quantitative and qualitative approaches, how can you guarantee the validity and reliability of your results?
- Combine quantitative and qualitative data without considering their reliability.
 - Use only quantitative data to ensure validity and reliability.
 - By using multiple data sources and establishing researcher reflexivity.⁵**
 - There is no need to ensure validity and reliability when using quantitative and qualitative approaches.
6. When should you use a comma in a sentence, and when should you avoid it?
- Place a comma before a conjunction to connect two independent clauses and avoid using a comma before a subordinate clause.⁶**
 - Commas are only used in lists and should be avoided in complex sentences.
 - Commas are only used in direct quotations and should be avoided in regular sentences.
 - Avoid using commas altogether, as they disrupt the flow of the sentence.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 25.

⁵ Ibid., 101.

⁶ Ibid., 159.

7. What name is given to the measures used to collect research data?
- Observations.
 - Questionnaires.
 - Interviews.
 - Instruments.**⁷
8. Which construction should you avoid with “not only...but also?”
- Avoid using “not only” to express two similar elements.
 - “Not only...but also” should not be used to describe “both x and y.”
 - “Not only...but also” must introduce new or surprising information after “but also.”**⁸
 - “Not only” should always be placed before “but also” in a construction.
9. How should you properly cite and present sources within the text of your research paper using the Chicago style?
- Include the author’s last name, publication year, and page number within parentheses after the quote or paraphrase in Chicago style.**⁹
 - In Chicago style, only include in-text citations for direct quotations, not paraphrases.

⁷ James P. Sampson, Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 43.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (Brussels: European Commission Publication Office, 2021), 57-58.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 237.

- Use the author's initials and publication year in parentheses after the quote or paraphrase.
- In Chicago style, use footnotes or endnotes for in-text citations.

10. How to write a clear, structured problem statement for a thesis?

- Define critical concepts, present the context and current state of knowledge, and formulate a research question and hypotheses.
- Start with the conclusion, then write the introduction and outline.
- Give an exhaustive description of the theoretical framework unrelated to the subject.
- Situate the subject in its scientific context, identify a problem or gap, and formulate a research question and objectives.¹⁰**

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 83-84.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition. Brussels: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation. A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition. Brussels: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.